

SUSTAINABLE TOURISM
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Abstract

Purpose: *The aim of this research is to throw light on importance of sustainable tourism and potential benefits of the same by supporting the tourism industry to develop economy of India and also to preserve the natural resources which are limited.*

Introduction: *Travel is integral part of any traveler and one of the important parts of tourism. In last decade there is lot of growth in tourism sector. There is a need to pay attention in this sector so that all the travelers will not just visit India but will go back with good memories and they will choose to visit destinations again and they would recommend to many. It is the efforts of Government, the travel industry and the local community need to work together to protect the environment. Today even hospitality industry works closely to preserve the planet.*

Methodology: *The literature review follows analyzing research articles written by researchers.1) to review information available about sustainable tourism and relation of sustainable tourism to hospitality industry.2) collect data of government website which resembles the economical impact on hospitality industry during pandemic.3) interpreting data into graph or in a pie chart. 4) Reach to a conclusion and findings based on the data interpreted.*

Findings: *Finding of our research will be: 1. To understand travelers are aware of importance of sustainable tourism, 2. Analysis of government policies and strategies to motivate hospitality industry to preserve natural resources and contribute in Indian economy.*

Keywords: *Sustainable Tourism, policies and strategies, Hospitality industry, foreign guests, destination, local community*

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Introduction:

Sustainable Tourism refers to Tourism takes care of its current and future socio-economic environmental impacts, reviewing needs of visitors, the industry and the needs of the host communities. Sustainable Tourism consideratse the needs of the present without comprising the future generations to meet their own needs. Sustainable development in tourism is necessary due to limited resources and significant concern about the environment. Offering Respect to the socio-cultural authenticity of host community is important in sustainable Tourism

When we think of sustainable tourism, we think of Individual behavior, family relationships, collective life styles, moral conduct, creative expressions, traditional ceremonies and community organization. Preservation of culture, natural resource management, waste management, corporate and social ethics in tourism is issues that influence other industries and sectors. However, the impact of tourism goes beyond the tangible economic effects of revenue and foreign exchange earnings.

Definition:

The United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) defines Sustainable Tourism as ‘Tourism that takes full account of its current and future economic, social and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment and host communities’. The German Forum on Environment and Development elaborates that ‘Sustainable Tourism has to meet social, cultural, ecological and economic requirements. Sustainable tourism holds a long-term view, for present and future generations, ethically and socially just and culturally adapted, ecologically viable and economically sensible and productive’.

History:

First thought of sustainable tourism was discussed in United Nations Conference on the Human Environment held in Stockholm, Sweden in 1972. This stands the first world conference which focused on “the environment” “a major issue”. The participants accepted a series of principles to achieve sound management of the environment including the Stockholm Declaration and Action Plan for the Human Environment and several resolutions. The Stockholm Declaration positioned environmental issues at the head of international concerns and started a dialogue between developed and developing countries. The Commission on Sustainable Development (CSD) was produced to examine and report on implementation of the Earth Summit agreements. Accordingly, the “Earth Summit + 5” at New York evaluated how countries, international organizations and sectors of civil society had responded to the challenge of the Earth Summit.

The Committee on Tourism and Sustainability (CTS), a Committee set up by the UNWTO – World Tourism Organization a United Nations Specialized Agency focuses on Sustainable Tourism Development. The focus areas include Biodiversity, Climate Change; Plastics pollution due to Tourism, Hotel Energy Solutions, and The One Planet Sustainable Tourism Programme is committed to support the recovery of the tourism sector from COVID-19 crisis as outlined within the One Planet Vision for a Responsible Recovery of the Tourism Sector.

Implementation of sustainable tourism principles requires:

- Optimal use of environmental resources that comprise a key element in tourism development, maintaining essential ecological processes and serving to conserve natural heritage and biodiversity.
- Conserve one’s cultural heritage and traditional values, and contribute to understanding inter-cultural and tolerance.
- Ensuring long-term economic operations, providing socio-economic benefits to all stakeholders that are fairly distributed, employment development and social services to host communities, and contributing to decrease poverty.

Role of Hospitality Industry in sustainable tourism:

The hospitality Industry along with tourism industry is creating many job opportunities for the mass. It is necessary to understand their role in sustainable tourism. In 1997 ‘the Orchid ‘was the first Ecotel which came up in Mumbai. They believed in recycling and today many leading hotels followed the footsteps as they contribute to save water, energy

which is limited.

Recycle water:

As there is scarcity of water, the amount of water which is used in bathing, Laundering and waste water is treated separately and reused to water the plants in the gardens, lawns in and around the Hotels. Hotels which are in hilly areas do Rainwater harvesting to save several liters of water.

Reuse energy:

To heat water, the leading brands are using solar panels. The low energy consumption LED lights are used in the guestrooms. The use of Keycards system, where the electricity of the room gets cut post the guest leaves the room automatically to save electricity.

Eco-friendly practices:

1. To avoid using plastic bottles, a glass bottles are used.
2. In fact the guest is also requested to be part of ‘save planet programme’ where the bath linen, the bed linen is laundered once in two to three days to save amount of material, water and electricity gets used up.
3. Instead of cut flowers, indoor plants are used in the guestrooms.
4. Maintaining heritage sites by not littering the place. Requesting the traveller to use bi-cycles to go for nearby places to avoid noise pollution.

Policies and strategies planned to boost sustainable tourism in India:

Realizing the importance of sustainable tourism, Prime Minister Modi has taken significant steps to promote Tourism. It has been recognized by them that tourism and Hospitality have potential to bring foreign revenue in the country.

1. From 2016, the government started to create the world class tourism related infrastructure to attract tourists as every year there is growth in foreign footfall..Rs.2261.50 cr has been sanctioned for 21 states and union territories to improve the infrastructure which needed the most.
2. The National Mission for Pilgrimage Rejuvenation and Spiritual Augmented Drive (PRASAD) scheme was launched by Ministry for the development and beautification of pilgrimage sites to increase the growth of domestic tourists. It has been also noted post covid 2019, there is a growth in domestic tourism.
3. Extending E-tourist visa has been done by the government. The Mobile app for Tourists, also Incredible India help line has been introduced.
4. They have also under taken 100 monuments to be developed as Model monuments, where it will have wi-fi, security signage where the short films will be showed on importance of monuments and sign boards on Swachh Bharat Abhiyan,The examples are Humayuns Tomb,Delhi,Leh palace{Leh},Elephanta caves(Mumbai).
5. The government also plans for skills development jobs in the field of Hospitality and Tourism.
6. The Ministry of Tourism has introduced Comprehensive Sustainable Tourism Criteria (STCI) for major segments of the tourism industry. That is mainly accommodations, tour operators, Beaches, Backwaters, Lakes and Rivers.
7. The Ministry is renewing Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the Responsible Tourism Society of India (RTSOI).
8. The ministry is also involving Eco Tourism Society of India (ESOI) to inform and educate tourism stakeholders and ensuring promoting Sustainable and Responsible practices in the tourism industry.
9. The target group includes hoteliers, tour operators, individuals from transport industry, resort managers, tourist

guides, community representatives and government departments (culture, forest, environment, Archaeological Survey of India (ASI), museums, district officials) etc.

10. A total of 5 such Workshops at Jaipur, Goa, Guwahati, Bhopal and Ahmedabad have been held so far.

Sustainable tourism involves local community, overall area development and a responsible traveler who visits the place for a shorter period. Hence they should avoid littering the place with plastics and harming the plants.

Sustainable tourism is also conscious efforts made by government, the locals and the traveler to remove the poverty, to remove unemployment and to preserve the culture, respecting tradition and custom.

Benefits:

The mainly three benefits are there 1) benefits to environment 2) help local communities 3) economic advantages.

As per the statistic of Ministry of Tourism of India In the Year 2020 FTA(Foreign Tourist Arrival) were 24.62 million (Jan to Nov)(Provisional) with a growth of -74.6% over same period of the previous year. During 2020, a total of 8.38 million (Jan-Nov) foreign tourists arrived on e-Tourist Visa registering a growth of -67.2%. From 2014 onwards, Ministry of Tourism has started to compile the arrivals of NRIS on annual basis and there were 6.98 million arrivals of NRIs in India during 2019. In concordance with UNWTO, ITA(International Tourist Arrival) include both FTAs and Arrivals of NRIs. In the year 2019, there were 17.91 million ITAs in India.

FEE(Foreign Exchange Earnings) during the period during Jan 2020 – March 2020 were Rs.44,203 crores (Provisional estimates) with a growth of -15.6% over same period of previous year. FEEs during the period during Jan 2020 – March 2020 were US\$ 6.159 billion (Provisional estimates) with a growth of -17.1% over same period of previous year. Domestic tourism continues to be an important contributor to the sector. As per the data furnished by State/UT Governments and other information available with the Ministry of Tourism, there were 2321.98 million domestic tourist visits all over the country during the year 2019.

Conclusion:

The Sustainable tourism gaining importance as it is a win-win situation for the traveler, the local community and for the nature which we would like to conserve. One needs to understand that it will not be able to make these changes overnight but the constant efforts of the traveler, the locals who would cooperate and with the support of the government of India its feasible we need to accelerate the entire process where the traveler needs to respect sentiments, tradition and customs of the locals, also conserve the nature. This will also give the locals employment to the locals and in turn improve the economy of our country. If we need to succeed, add greenery ,we will have to protect our Planet Earth and one way to enter doing this is through sustainable Tourism. We need to tackle global challenges regarding climatic changes.

This traveler is not cost conscious, in fact they are ready to pay more. They want to experience uniqueness of the place These traveler value ‘authenticity’ of the place, culture and food. More and more travelers are turning to responsible tourists who value planet earth and they are eco sensitive. If we wish to give these natural resources to future generation, then we have to preserve the natural flora and fauna.

Sustainable tourism is about we care. There is a need to develop government strategy by deciding on Tourism vision, objective and also study again the supply and demand development strategies, it will bring desirable outcome as the planning process involves many levels of government at national Ministerial level as well as partnership with the industry and the private sector. More of Integrated approach is required in tourism development.

Key words: Sustainable Tourism, Hospitality Industry, Strategies and policies, Socio economic Development

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